

Solutions to Help Students in Vietnam's Vocational Education Institutes Develop a Cultural Lifestyle

Minh Pham Ngoc¹, Kien Dinh Trung², Lanh Nguyen Thi³

^{1,2,3} Ninh Binh Mechanical College

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 18 July 2022	Vietnamese adolescents urgently need to receive ethical and lifestyle education so that they can become conscientious students, adhere to the law, adhere to cultural norms, and meet academic requirements. Our research focuses on recommending strategies to support students in having a fulfilling and encouraging learning environment. The actions we suggest include creating catchphrases, planning student learning movements, setting a positive example, imparting life skills, and working with the school's administration and departments.
Corresponding Author: Lanh Nguyen Thi	
KEYWORDS: Education, Culture, Study, Lecturers And Students.	

1. INTRODUCTION

"Building an advanced Vietnamese culture imbued with national identity so that the culture can truly become the become an endogenous strength, a driving force for national development and national defense," states the resolution of the 13th Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam (February 2, 2021). Boost financial support for cultural advancement. The talents, intelligence, and qualities of the Vietnamese people are the most crucial center, goal, and driving force of the country's development. It is our mission to build, develop, and create the most favorable environment and social conditions to arouse patriotic tradition, national pride, belief, and aspiration to develop a prosperous and happy country.

Vietnam Party and State have again reaffirmed at the recent National Cultural Conference in 2021 that "culture has a very vital significance, being the spiritual foundation and driving force for the development of society." It is crucial to put an emphasis on cultural education, creating lifestyles, and promoting cultural diversity if culture is to truly serve as the spiritual foundation of society, the aim and the impetus behind industrialization, modernization, innovation, and integration. Education facilities should promote a healthy cultural lifestyle.

Effectively executing Party Central Committee Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW on Fundamental and Comprehensive Renovation of Education and Training in the Period of 2021-2025, Educational Institutions, The vocational sector has undergone recent modifications, including the integration of ethical and cultural education to the technical skills training provided to employees. Therefore, creating a vibrant cultural life for university

students those enrolled in the current vocational school system crucial to fostering the development of ideas, morals, and ethics and personality. Vietnamese workers must concurrently strengthen their professional skills, attitudes, professional ethics, and healthy cultural lifestyles in order to improve their vocational abilities and support long-term professional development.

There are still some students whose behavior is not in accordance with social standards and not in accordance with the school's discipline, despite the fact that studies on students' lifestyle ethics, Mac, V.T (1998); Nguyen, T.H (2018) find that the vast majority of students at vocational education institutions are good, adapt the requirements, and work hard. Some another students have broken the law, fought, shown disregard for friends and the community, neglected their studies, were game addicts, smoked, and these actions have had an impact on their peers, conflict the regulations, decorum, and order of the school. Since then, we have developed a number of strategies to work with educational institutions to promote a healthy and good cultural lifestyle in order to achieve the objective of developing high-quality human resources for the economy and societal demands of the future.

2. SOLUTIONS TO PROMOTE A HEALTHY CULTURAL LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENTS AND THOSE ENROLLED IN VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS

2.1. Create and enhance rules and catchphrases that are appropriate for each training institution in order to better student management.

(1) The content of these agreements should be explicit regarding what an apprentice may and cannot

accomplish during the school's learning process. (2) A system of rewards for students who follow the rules correctly. (3) Punishments for students who disobey school rules.

The information contained in the documents governing the administration of students and apprentices should be precisely drafted, regulate student study and training, and at the same time, reflect the educational objectives of the institution. The goal of vocational education is to develop a team of knowledgeable individuals who are both moral and gifted. It is essential to create a system of welcoming and instructive signs and slogans for students, and to place them in lecture halls, practice spaces, and classrooms.

The slogan's message might be something like: "Attitude over skill," "I am confident," "I will succeed here," "The heart is worth three times as much as talent," etc. In order to improve learners' interest and drive to learn, each profession should also have its own catchphrases, such as "Cooking is an art, and the chef is an artist".

To foster a positive atmosphere that contributes to the development of each student's personality, way of living, and creative potential as well as that of their teachers, regulations on student management in vocational education institutions should be developed that are precise and unambiguous.

2.2. Starting the campaign for educational emulation

Implement initiatives like "Continue to promote learning and following Ho Chi Minh's ideology, morals, and style" to enhance the standard of instruction and training provided to instructors and students in classrooms. To give students exposure to a variety of learning situations, hold numerous professional competitions, such as international, national, ministerial, and provincial vocational skills competitions. Numerous typical and exceptional examples have emerged in schools as a result of these initiatives. These emulation exercises require two components. Students are engaged and active learners, and all organizational parts of the school should be paying attention and working in unison.

In reality, there are still certain restrictions on how university students learn, such as the fact that they are not very active, are too lazy to study, are not well-trained, and that the coordination of movement organization across units is not very efficient. The Party Committee, Board of Directors, leaders of faculties and departments in universities, and units, officials, teachers, and employees must all pay full and strict attention. This is the solution for the following stage. Students are accountable for taking part in the movement and exerting effort. Emulation movement organization needs to be innovative in substance and rich in form, and it should place importance on the task of preliminary, summarizing, complete, and correct assessment of the movement. The process of rewarding and disciplining is also rigorous.

2.3 In vocational education settings, emulating typical examples of students' cultural lifestyles

Students are enthusiastic individuals who are eager to learn, eager to try new things, and eager for societal improvements. Set excellent instances of self-study and self-cultivation of life ethics as a result of this. The school must create an example for its students by showing them how to succeed in a variety of endeavors, including science, art, and sports, while also overcoming obstacles to learning. The majority of students actively integrate into the diverse cultural milieu while yet maintaining their national fashion and traditions and leading healthy lifestyles.

To encourage pupils to have needs, incentives to strive, practice, have a sense of learning and reaching out, the school conducts sharing and exchanges between students with good achievements and other students. Be assertive.

Schools should set good examples in learning, training, and student movement activities and promptly recognize and award them. This will help to encourage and motivate students to keep learning and growing. Schools should sustain flag-raising events each month, presenting examples of students who had outstanding accomplishments over the month to praise and praise before each hour of flag-raising. Excellent pupils are also encouraged by the school to sign up for classes that would prepare them to join the Communist Party of Vietnam in the future.

2.4. Encourage the teaching of life skills and soft skills, and plan a variety of cultural and artistic events, sports, voluntary work, and student volunteer projects.

Create thematic lectures and include topics relating to soft skills education and life skills education for apprentices in the curriculum, such as modules on goal-setting, time management, managing one's emotions, appreciating one's worth, communicating, working in a team, and problem-solving. By doing so, you can contribute to students' spiritual growth and development as well as their internal strength, self-assurance, and sense of self, all of which will help them lead fulfilling lives.

Promote the learning and training process for students by organizing cultural and artistic events, physical activity programs, and sports. In addition to promoting student health, taking part in these events fosters camaraderie and friendliness among students of various academic levels and career paths at the school. This will assist students in finding a healthy balance between work and play and in mentally unwinding so that they can learn and practice to their full potential.

President Ho Chi Minh, the great leader of Vietnam's country, saw art as a popular spiritual activity that aided in the struggle for national independence and the advancement of society during his lifetime. Therefore, a variety of cultural and artistic events are planned at schools, especially around significant anniversaries like the Founding Day of the Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union on February 26. the date the

school was founded (June 3); Uncle's Ho Chi Minh birthday (May 19); Vietnam Teachers' Day (November, 20)... Students should also routinely practice and participate in sporting events sponsored by the Youth Union, such as drag competitions, table tennis, football, and volleyball, which will help them unwind after difficult lessons.

2.5. Improve the leadership of the school in creating a cultural life for pupils.

In order to address cultural and spiritual demands, to develop scientific thinking, aesthetic capacity, and vitality, party committees and school administrators must pay particular attention to and direct the development of a good cultural life. Students' development of personality and inventiveness. educating faculty, staff, and students about the importance of a healthy cultural lifestyle for a person's overall development Regulations govern how to commend teachers who serve kids properly during the academic year.

2.6. Promote all initiatives to help students develop a cultural lifestyle by maximizing the effectiveness of departmental and faculty synergies in educational institutions.

Each officer and lecturer in every school, as well as the operational departments, unions, and associations, must set an example for students to follow when studying. The departments' activities are always focused on actively assisting students, fostering a supportive environment for them as they connect and address their needs. The departments of Student Affairs, Finance, and Training that deal with students on a regular basis need to be excellent, enthusiastic, and most actively encourage students.

3. CONCLUSION

The development of a cultural lifestyle at institutions of vocational education nowadays is influenced by both positive and negative societal forces. Each school must function as a unit of unity, above and below, with the same purpose in order to improve the quality of establishing a cultural lifestyle and meet the construction requirements of each school in order to develop a robust and complete school.

The solutions listed above are interconnected. Each solution is accomplished as a result of other solutions as well as a cause. To appropriately handle the concentration and emphasis during the implementation process, it is vital to base your decisions on the unique circumstances of each school. The quality of constructing students' cultural lives in vocational education institutions would undoubtedly increase if these solutions are properly applied, directly influencing the development of apprentices' all-encompassing personalities.

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